

Effect of ZrO₂ additive in reaction sintering of bauxite and titania

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Raw bauxite and titania with molar ratio of Al₂O₃ : TiO₂ as 1 : 1 were wet milled with varying amount of ZrO₂. The milled powder, after drying, was pressed into compacts, which were then sintered at various temperatures from 1400° to 1550°. ZrO₂ additive (14.12% maximum) influenced the magnitude of sintering and quality of the sintered product.

Aluminium titanate arouses commercial interest as a consequence of its low thermal expansion coefficient comparable to fused silica and also a comparatively high melting point of 1800°. It may be used to obtain ceramics having low α value and at the same time can have quite high service temperature. It has find a number of commercial applications as exhaust port liners in both petrol and diesel engines. It is also under serious consideration for use as manifold inserts, piston crowns and turbo-charger liners etc.

Wohlformm *et al.*¹ prepared two sets of Al₂TiO₅ based material both monoclinic and ZrO₂/mullite particulate reinforced by slip casting of mixtures of Al₂O₃, TiO₂, ZrSiO₄ and subsequent reaction sintering. Pereira *et al.*² studied Al₂TiO₅ phase decomposition after adding controlled amount of SiO₂, ZrO₂ and MgO. Montoya *et al.*³ prepared series of Al₂O₃-TiO₂ mixed oxides with different TiO₂ concentrations (6, 14 and 44 wt%) and the single oxides were prepared by the sol-gel method. Giorano⁴ carried out studies on microstructures and thermal expansion of Al₂TiO₅, MgTiO₃ obtained by reaction sintering.

In the present investigation the effect of ZrO₂ as an additive on the sintering of raw bauxite and titania towards formulations of aluminium titanate was studied.

Results and discussion

The molar ratio of Al₂O₃ and TiO₂ was kept at 1 : 1. The specific surface area of the raw material powders was 130 m² g⁻¹, which was sufficient enough for better compaction. The DTA curves (Figs. not shown) of bauxite and titania show an endothermic peak at 300° and non-existence of either endothermic or exothermic peak

Fig. 1. Variation of volume shrinkage with temperature : (♦) Batch I, (□) Batch II, (*) Batch III, (Δ) Batch IV.

respectively. The shrinkage of the briquettes (Fig. 1) increased with increase in temperature upto 1500° and decreased after that for a particular batch composition. At a particular temperature, shrinkage increased with increase in ZrO₂ content.

Apparent porosity values (Fig. 2) of the sintered compacts decreased from Batch I to Batch IV at a particular temperature of firing. But the decrease of apparent porosity at 1500° is much higher compared to that at 1550°. This might be due to higher sintering and densification of the samples at 1500°. Gradual increase of bulk density (Fig. 3) with temperature indicated positive relation of sinterability with temperature.

Fig. 2. Variation of apparent porosity with temperature : (◆) Batch I, (□) Batch II, (★) Batch III, (Δ) Batch IV.

From an analysis of the true density values (Fig. 3) it can be concluded that as the density increase occurred in steps, it was a clear indication of reaction sintering process and formations of aluminium titanate and densification occurred separately.

Fig. 3. Variation of density with temperature : (◆) Batch I, (□) Batch II, (★) Batch III, (Δ) Batch IV.

All the sintered products were subjected to thermal spalling i.e. heating at 800° for 10 min and then quenched in air for 10 min and the results are given in Table I. The above spalling resistance might be due to the formation of low expansion titanate phase with sharp grain boundaries with minimum glassy phase.

Variation in mechanical strength with temperature of firing for all the samples fired at all the temperatures as shown in Fig. 4.

From XRD diagram (Figs. not shown) of the samples, fired at 1550°, it can be noted that the major phase in all

Table 1. Determination of spalling resistance of pellets fired at different temperatures

Firing temp. (°C)	Sample batch number	Number of cycles withstood	Remarks
1400	I	30	No Crack
	II	30	"
	III	30	"
	IV	30	"
1500	I	30	"
	II	30	"
	III	30	"
	IV	30	"
1550	I	30	"
	II	30	"
	III	30	"
	IV	30	"

Fig. 4. Variation of mechanical strength with temperature : (◆) Batch I, (□) Batch II, (★) Batch III, (Δ) Batch IV.

the four batches was Al_2TiO_5 . $ZrTiO_4$ was major phase in Batch III and IV only and minor phase in Batch II, which can be correlated with increase of ZrO_2 from 4.85 to 14.12%.

The SEM analysis of Batch I samples (Figs. not shown) indicated distribution of Al_2TiO_5 phase. With the increase in ZrO_2 content, the microstructures which initially contained some sub-rounded particles, exhibited sharp edged crystals which are Al_2TiO_5 and may be minor amounts of $ZrTiO_4$. It is also observed that in Batch I, there is evidence of grain growth and densifications of Al_2TiO_5 crystalline phase. But in Batch II to Batch IV, the microstructure had changed significantly with formations of $ZrTiO_4$ crystals and their subsequent growth. The

microstructure also exhibited some transangular cracks in comparison to the samples fired at 1450°, which contained sub-rounded particles.

Conclusion :

Low expansion Al_2TiO_5 may be generated through reaction sintering of bauxite and TiO_2 at 1500°. With the incorporation of ZrO_2 (14.12%), the properties of the Al_2TiO_5 system improves to a great extent because of formation of $ZrTiO_4$ and subsequent consolidation of the system.

Experimental

Raw bauxite (Saurashtra), TiO_2 (A.R., 99.0%), ZrO_2 (A.R., 99.0%), Fe_2O_3 (A.R., 90.0%, LOI-8.0%) were used as the starting material for synthesis of aluminium titanate. The bauxite sample was analysed for SiO_2 -2.99%, Al_2O_3 -60.38%, Fe_2O_3 -1.85%, TiO_2 -1.83% and LOI-32.90%.

Required amount of raw bauxite and titania were taken in the molar ratio of $Al_2O_3 : TiO_2$ as 1 : 1, ZrO_2 was added in various amounts and 2% Fe_2O_3 level was maintained in all the four batches to act as stabilizer. Composition of the batches was given in Table 2.

DTA analysis of raw bauxite and titania was carried out with a NETZSCHSTA-409 analyser. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Nicolet FTIR spectrophotometer (Magna IR series II). Briquettes of samples were fabri-

Table 2. Composition of the batches (mole %)

Batch No.	ZrO_2	Al_2O_3	Titania	Fe_2O_3
I	0.0000	49.2409	49.2269	1.5321
II	4.8463	44.4609	49.1796	1.5132
III	11.3621	44.7654	42.1068	1.7651
IV	14.1221	35.2786	49.1262	1.4731

cated at a pressure of 2000 kg cm^{-2} in a hydraulic press without any extra binder. The briquettes were sintered at 1450, 1500 and 1550° respectively in a electrically heated muffle furnace with 2 hours of soaking period. The heating rate of the briquettes was 10°/min upto 1000° and then 5°/min to the final temperature of heat treatment.

X-Ray diffraction was recorded on a Philips PW-1730 diffractometer using CuK_{α} radiations. SEM photographs were taken on a S-530, Hitachi-Japan, Scanning Electron Microscope.

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